

A network diagram with various sized blue and grey nodes connected by thin lines, forming a complex web structure on the left side of the page.

D7.1 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION STRATEGY -v1

March 31, 2023

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Executive Summary

The 1st release of the Dissemination and Communication strategy outlines the process behind the development of the ENERATE communication and dissemination strategy and objectives. This deliverable aims to set a strategy to be applied during the overall implementation of the project. One of the main objective of the first realise of the strategy is to define the target audience and the project's stakeholders (in leason with T.5.1 Stakeholder mapping and engagement) and define the communication and dissemination activities to engage them.

The Dissemination and Communication strategy of ENERATE can be articulated into two main phases:

Phase I – Raise awareness/interest among key stakeholders (M1-M15): ENERATE will focus on establishing a common project identity, raising awareness and interest regarding the project's expected results, as well as, identifying the target groups and main project's stakeholders and plan the activities to reach them. During this phase the aim is as well to raise awareness about the ENERGATE Platform (the 1st public version roll-out to stakeholders is expected by M15) through the different communication channels and target groups identified in this deliverable.

Phase II – Enhance acceptance of ENERATE ICT-enabled solution and promoting the ENERATE platform (M15-Y3): ENERATE will focus on disseminating its solution as well as the ENERATE platform and its use with a view to clearly demonstrate the benefits and supporting future exploitation of results also after the project's end. Key activities to be conducted during Phase II include publications about project results, the organization of conferences, events, workshops, and participatory activities (e.g., labs) promoting knowledge exchange. In this phase, ENERATE will engage the target stakeholders at the national level, through the organisation of workshops and webinars in the partners' country and national language, and at the EU level through the organisation of a Final Event, if possible, in person in Brussels. The event will aim to link the projects' results with EU policy discussions and bring together high-level representatives from different organizations and institutions.

In the following sections of this deliverable, we will set the Dissemination and Communication strategy of ENERATE and identify the main project's stakeholders as well as provide a list of planned activities for the first year of implementation.

1. Introduction

It is common that the terms “communication” and “dissemination” are used interchangeably regarding promotion activities. This is neither entirely false nor entirely correct. Although communication and dissemination have indeed a lot in common, there are certain points which significantly differentiate them. As a starting point, communication and dissemination are both important as their main goal is to promote the project leading to awareness raising and increased interest, and finally enabling the project to make an impact. However, these two terms are different regarding the specific goal of promotion and the respective audience.

In particular, **communication** relates to the promotion of the project to general public in order to show the impact and benefits that it achieved, focusing on both the project and its results. On the other hand, **dissemination's** objective is to transfer the knowledge and results gained within the project to these particular audiences that are most probable to use them, focusing on the description and availability of the project's results.

Dissemination and communication are horizontal activities and concentrate on distributing the activities and results of ENEREGATE itself to a wide range of existing or potential stakeholders, belonging to different target groups. The purpose of dissemination and communication is not unique. The dissemination activities are aimed at achieving different goals, towards different targets, in different phases of a project, having (phase by phase) different material available. Communication of ENEREGATE results will take several forms and use a variety of tools. Some tools are expected to have a greater impact than others, and thus, their value to the aims of the project may differ.

1.1. Deliverable Overview

In Chapter 2 we will define the ENEREGATE target group and define the main project's stakeholders in liaison with WP5 (T.5.1 Stakeholder mapping and engagement), this serves as a plan and is linked to the following sections in which we will introduce the process of the Visual Identity creation (Chapter 3) followed by the ENEREGATE communication channels that have been put in place and will serve as a main dissemination tool for the project (Chapter 4). In Chapter 5 we will introduce the ENEREGATE Communication and Promotional Package in Chapter 6 we will outline the Scientific Publications and the target fixed. Chapter 7 focuses on the events ENEREGATE is targeting that have been categorized and are strictly linked to the target group identified in Chapter 2. Chapter 8 outlines the Communication, dissemination, and networking boosters' activities. Furthermore, in Chapter 9 we will introduce the reporting methodology (KPIs and monitoring) of the communications activities. To conclude, in Chapter 10 we outline a non-exhaustive list of activities planned for the first year of ENEREGATE implementation (M1-M12).

1.2. Deliverable Objectives

The aim of this deliverable is to develop a tailored strategy and plan for dissemination and communication with a view to effectively conveying the key messages of ENEREGATE to its target audiences as well as increasing the visibility of the project along with its activities and results, thus paving the road for a potential post-project deployment and uptake.

The communication and dissemination plan has been elaborated at the project start, listing objectives and messages, target groups and how to reach them, resources (tools, HR, time and budget), KPIs and evaluation mechanisms, risks and challenges as well as modus

operandi. The plan lists different channels to reach the several target groups, such as preferred communication methods, a social media pack for partners, relevant conferences and raise interest, identification of relevant media channels and synergies that could be created with other EU projects or networks. It includes the project identity and basic promotional package.

The plan will be evaluated and updated to ensure targeted events and channels are still valid and to add new ones.

1.3. Deliverable Update

This deliverable is written by REHVA with the collaboration of the WP7 leader IEECP and the coordinator and T7.2 leader NTUA and will be updated in M16.

2. Stakeholder Management Plan (SMP): identification of the target groups

The mapping of the main target groups of the project is listed below and will serve both WP5 and WP7. Each target group will be approached by communication and dissemination activities using specific messages leveraging that focus on the benefits they can accrue from the project and targeted channels. WP7 lists the engagement activities and the communication material that will be used for the dissemination and communication activities and targets for all the below groups mentioned.

Overall, target stakeholders are divided into three hierarchical levels: those in the first level are key users and beneficiaries of the ENERGATE platform; those in the second level may use the ENERGATE platform as a source of information to support their activities, though they are not key users; and those in the third level are not expected to become users of the ENERGATE platform, despite being potentially useful as amplifiers of the project's messages.

After mapping all stakeholders, key messages were designed for each segment, based on their potential interest in the ENERGATE platform, as identified for WP5. These key messages should guide the execution of all communication and dissemination activities, thus improving their impact and efficacy in promoting the adoption of the tool. They should also support the execution of the engagement strategy laid out in *D5.1 - Stakeholder engagement plan with consultation guide*.

Table 1: Stakeholder mapping and plan

Level	Segment	Subsegment	Key message	Key channels
First	Financial Stakeholders	Private financing bodies (private)	It's easier to identify the most attractive bundle to get the desired impact in building projects.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Events • Website • Newsletter • Communication collaterals (infographics, briefs, non-scientific articles...)
		Public financing bodies (public)	It's easier to identify the most attractive bundle to get the desired impact in building projects.	
		Fund managers	You can better define interesting investment opportunities by comparing attractive "bundles" of materials.	
		Investment consultants	You can better define interesting investment opportunities by comparing attractive "bundles" of materials.	
		Private investors	You can find raw materials to buy, bundle them on the platform and resell them with profit.	
		Banks	You can better define interesting investment opportunities by comparing attractive "bundles" of materials.	

First	Building Stakeholders	ESCOS	You can enter the data of your services and compare the impact with other services that have been shared on the platform.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Events • Website • Newsletters • Mainstream Media • Social Media • Communication collaterals (infographics, briefs, non-scientific articles...)
		Project developers	You can enter the data of your building(s) into the platform and compare performance with others.	
		Building owners	You can enter the data of your building(s) into the platform and compare performance with others.	
		Asset managers	You can enter the data of your building(s) into the platform and compare performance with others.	
Second	Policy makers and policy support	Policy makers	ENERGATE will derive in policy recommendations, policy briefs, lessons learnt that can support your work.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletters • Events • Website • Communication collaterals (infographics, briefs, non-scientific articles...)
		Policy support organisations	You can access to accurate and centralized information on funded EE projects, funding opportunities, and achieved outcomes.	
Second	Research institutes and universities		You can learn from case studies about the demands of financial stakeholders. The ENERGATE research and results can provide inputs to your own research.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conferences • Scientific Publications • Events • Social Media • Website
Third	Others	NGO	You can find funding opportunities for your projects and learn from case studies.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication collaterals (infographics,

		Media	N/A	briefs, non-scientific articles...) • Website • Mainstream Media • Social Media
		General public	N/A	
		Technical Chambers	You can learn from case studies about the demands of financial stakeholders.	
		Energy Associations	You can find funding opportunities for your projects and learn from case studies.	
		Real Estate	You can find funding opportunities for your projects and learn from case studies.	

3. Visual Identity

Creating a common project's visual identity is key to raising awareness and interest regarding ENERGATE's future activities and outcomes. From the first month of the project, the consortium worked and collaborated in the process of making a strong project identity.

This visual identity package includes the following items:

- Project logo and colours
- Typeface
- Banners for project website, email signature and social media profile (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook)
- Newsletter cover
- Brand identity manual
- Deliverable (docx) and presentation (pptx) templates

3.1. ENERGATE Logo

During the kick-off meeting, held in Athens in January 2023, partners were asked to vote and provide inputs on the ENERGATE logo propositions and the ENERGATE colour palette. Eight different logo options have been presented and voted on using a Google form (<https://forms.gle/sEqKaVnWnkdmLYj6>).

More details about the logo proposition and the logo selections process are given in ANNEX I of this deliverable.

The screenshot shows a Google Form titled "ENERGATE LOGO" with the question "Which logo better represents ENERGATE?". Below the question is a link to sign in to Google. There are two options presented:

Option 1: Two circular logos. The first is a green circle with a white stylized 'E' and 'G' inside. The second is a dark green circle with a white stylized 'E' and 'G' inside. Below each logo is the word "ENERGATE" and "Energy Efficiency Marketplace".

Option 2: Two circular logos. The first is a light green circle with the word "ENERGATE" inside. The second is a dark green circle with the word "ENERGATE" inside.

Figure 1: ENERGATE logo selection

Figure 2: ENERGATE logo v.1

Logo Construction

Figure 3: ENERGATE logo construction

In addition, four colours' variations of the logo have been created, to be used in the different communication channels and in all ENERGATE documents (Deliverables, presentations, events agenda etc.).

Figure 4: ENERGATE logo colours variation

3.1.1. ENERGATE Brand Manual

To create a common visual identity, it is essential to aggregate all the information in one document that sets the rules to follow for the whole consortium. Following this purpose, ENERGATE has created its own brand manual that sets the basis for all communication and dissemination activities and products. The brand manual is articulated in four main sections:

- Verbal Identity
- Logo Guidelines
- Typography
- Colours

The brand manual has been published on the project repository and is accessible to all partners. All partners will have to follow the guidelines set in the brand manual for the overall duration of the project.

Verbal Identity

Page 03

Words

Brand Colors

Page 16

Logo Colors

Figure 5: ENERGATE brand manual

3.2. ENERGATE Templates

As part of the ENERGATE Visual Identity we have developed a Word template for ENERGATE which can be used both for formal deliverables as well as (other) formal documents for the projects (events' agendas, minutes from General Assemblies etc.). Similarly, a PowerPoint template has been developed as well to ensure a common identity at events. All templates are available in the project repository and will be used for internal and external communication.

Figure 6: ENERGATE deliverable template

Figure 7: ENERGATE PowerPoint Template

Figure 8: ENERGATE agenda template

In addition, for the ENERGATE 2 different banners have been created:

- Newsletter banner
- Social media banner

Figure 9: ENERGATE Newsletter & Social Media banner

4. ENERGATE Digital Outreach

Several project-related tools will be leveraged to communicate about the project digitally: a website, newsletters, social media and the use of platforms as multipliers.

Table 2: ENERGATE Digital Outreach plan

Mechanism	Phase I: Raise awareness/interest among key stakeholders (M1-M15)	Phase II: Enhance acceptance of ENERGATE ICT-enabled solution and promoting the ENERGATE platform (M15-Y3):
Project Website	I) Design & Development of an intuitive and responsive project's website. Promotion of objectives and project scope.	II) Regular update of the website content; Watch the website's analytics to measure impact and provide content of interest. Promote the platform website.
Social Media Campaign	I) Establishment of presence in Social Media Reproduce relevant content & monitor relevant hashtags; Upload public material; Follow influencers of the domain; Engage with other projects and initiatives.	II) Promote the project's outcomes, the platform, and events; Interact with followers to get feedback; Answer comments and private messages on the various channels; Upload public material; Reproduce relevant content and monitor relevant hashtags.
Newsletters	I) Newsletter to announce the project's launch and the website.	II) Newsletter to announce the significant events/results and platform release.

4.1. Website

The ENERGATE website (energate-project.eu) development is of significant importance for the effective promotion of the ENERGATE action, as it will contribute to target groups' awareness raising and it will create interest and attract potential contributions to the whole effort.

The project website aims to:

- Ensuring open access to project public results;
- Supporting the exploitation: results will be available after the project end (2 years after the project's end)

The website is under development and will include basic project information, such as title, logo, brief description, objectives, methodology (ENERGATE Approach "Fetch-Process-Deliver"), work structure, expected contribution, and consortium. Moreover, the website will contain information on the events organised by the project, as well as the events in which ENERGATE partners have participated in, which are called external event. In addition, the

website will ensure open access to project results (public ones) easily and freely downloadable.

The website will focus on sharing more digestible descriptions about ENERGate activities and will avoid typical “project language” (e.g. deliverables, outputs, etc.), talking rather about objectives, successes, services, etc. A dedicated ENERGate page will be also created on the websites of all consortium partners.

The website will contain at a minimum (but not limited to, as it will be constantly enhanced) the following:

- Information about the project, including Objectives, Methodology, Contribution, Participants etc.;
- News and Events with relative information such as agendas, photos, events’ scope, etc.;
- Library with main outputs, deliverables, reports, scientific publications, articles;
- Communication resources (brochure, video, infographics, newsletters, press releases, synergies with relevant projects etc).

Figure 10: ENERGate website initial structure

The website and electronic communication practices will be compliant with the current EU legislation on personal data and communications - General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Compliance with GDPR will be ensured in the case of third-party tools used in managing electronic dissemination via the web, such as website traffic analytics, embedded multimedia, electronic communications’ automation tools and other functionalities.

The basic pages are defined as follows:

The **Home** page welcomes visitors to the ENERGate project and has a slideshow which will be enhanced with photos from ENERGate News and Events. The most recent news regarding the project can be easily accessed in this page. Moreover, it has the “Newsletter Sign-Up” section which provides the ability to subscribe in order to receive newsletters. Additionally, links to the social media (Twitter, LinkedIn) are incorporated in the Home page.

Figure 11: ENERGate website – Home page

The **About** page includes all the information relating to the ENERGate project:

- The **ENERGate Objectives** sub-page provides a small description of the project and its objectives.
- The **Methodology** sub-page presents briefly the steps of the ENERGate scheme and their main outputs as well as the case study countries that are participating in the project.
- The **Pilots** give information of the pilots.
- The **Contribution** sub-page briefly presents the benefits and contribution of the project for the several target groups that the project has.
- The **Who we are** sub-page hosts an accordion-style table with all the consortium partners and links to their relevant websites for more information about each partner.

Figure 12: ENEREGATE website – About pages

The **News and Events** page is divided in the sub-pages as follows:

- The **News** page provides news and articles concerning the project, as well as newsletters produced by the ENEREGATE project. In addition, announcements of the project workshops and relative events at national and European level will be circulated through the particular domain.
- At the **Events** page all relevant organisation details of the project workshops are uploaded, including all the informational material (agenda, presentations, photos).

The **Library** page constitutes an information page including useful material, such as deliverables, related studies and other related scientific publications. More particularly, the **Results** sub-page will include all the public project deliverables to be downloaded by the visitors, while the **Publications** sub-page includes all the scientific publications, articles, online reports that has been published to promote the ENEREGATE methodology and results among the target groups.

The **Communication** will consists of sub-pages, i.e. **Media**, **Newsletters**, **Synergies**, each one providing relevant information on: the **promotional material** (brochures, infographics, videos, posters, etc.), the **electronic communications** (ENEREGATE Newsletters, ENEREGATE Press Releases) and the **synergies** with projects, initiatives and organisations, as well as existing works of other platforms related to ENEREGATE, including links to their websites.

The **ENEREGATE Energy Efficiency Marketplace** will have a redirection to the main output of the project which is the marketplace.

Finally, the **Contact** page provides a contact form and comprehensive contact information of the project manager and dissemination leader of the project.

The ENERGATE dissemination strategy foresees two milestones regarding the website's traffic, in order to ensure and tangibly display the success of the dissemination activities and promotion of the project. For this purpose, the *Google Analytics* (GA) service will be added, to track in detail the visitor traffic of the ENERGATE website. GA offers detailed statistics about the website's traffic and the traffic

sources. It will also provide information regarding the number of ENERGATE website visitors, as well as the percentage of new visitors, the number of visits and pageviews, allowing to monitor the website's success as a means of dissemination and information provision. It is foreseen that the ENERGATE website will attract at least 5,000 unique visitors per year and 15% return visitors. Last but not least, the website will also support the project's exploitation strategy for at least 2 years after its completion.

The official launch of the website will be done in M5 – May 2023. In addition, all partners will create a dedicated ENERGATE webpage in their institutions' website promoting project scope, partners, news, events.

4.2. Social Media identity

Social Media and particularly Twitter, LinkedIn, have become platforms that are easily accessible to anyone with internet access. Increased communication for organisations fosters brand awareness. Additionally, social media serves as a relatively inexpensive platform for organisations to implement marketing campaigns and effectively disseminate outcomes and associated information. With the proliferation of niche sites and communities on the Internet, it is becoming increasingly important to target long tail search terms and cast a wide net.

In this framework, exploiting all the assets social media have to offer, while considering the related risks, could be truly beneficial in successfully disseminating the ENERGATE scope, activities and outcomes. Through social networking ENERGATE will gain wide access to the power of web publishing to non-technical users cost-effectively, while e.g. LinkedIn, Twitter users drive traffic to ENERGATE website, articles, workshops, etc.

Links to ENERGATE social media accounts will be added to all the pages of the ENERGATE website.

Posts and tweets include announcements for events, reports and publications, dissemination activities, new dissemination material, several achievements and results. Photos are also uploaded from ENERGATE events and interventions in conferences.

ENERGATE will adapt different strategies according to the social media channels. For [Twitter](https://twitter.com/Energate_eu)¹, it is important to mention that the Dissemination team had initially in the Kick off meeting discussed not to create a new account in Twitter, but take advantage of the partners' institution accounts' followers and having NTUA's account as the main twitter account that would lead the process. However, in the course of the project it was decided to continue with a separate account since this may have some additional benefits.

Having our own account will allow us to make more regular/daily posts about the project and related research. For example, the several campaigns that we are going to launch would have

¹ https://twitter.com/Energate_eu

more impact if they are promoted through a dedicated account and promoted/ retweeted through the institutional ones to gain visibility.

A separate profile will give us the opportunity to tweet the posts of other projects and create synergies, while more generic posts could be done, related to news and advances on building renovation, energy efficiency financing, new regulations, best practices, etc. To this end, the separate account could serve as a repository of news related to the project advances and the energy efficiency financing in buildings topic in general.

Last but not least, in terms of analytics, with the separate account, the way to track the data may could be easier through the tweeter analytics service, while we will be able to connect the account with google analytics in order to monitor the flow on the website through our social networks.

For [LinkedIn](#)², a separate page has been created in order for partners to share the project updates more easily and make sure not to go against their corporate communication guidelines. So far the LinkedIn account, which runs from 26th January 2023 and it was created in order to announce the Kick off Meeting, has 183 followers, 3,500 impressions and 147 reactions.

Figure 13: ENERGATE Social Media

² <https://www.linkedin.com/company/energate-project>

NTUA DSS Lab @DSS_Lab · Jan 26

🌟 Time to kick-off!

💡 Interested in how we will create an #EnergyEfficiency Aggregation platform for Sustainable Investments?

🔍 While we get our website ready, follow our hashtag #ENERGATE and you will soon learn more about our advances!

Figure 14: Post about ENERGATE KoM on the NTUA DSS Lab Twitter account

ENERGATE Project
 180 followers
 2mo • Edited •

🔥 Time to kick-off!
 ⚡ Our project **ENERGATE Project** will deliver an effective, ICT-enabled, energy efficiency marketplace bringing together energy services and sustainable finance to accelerate the renovation rate of buildings by increasing the chances for projects to be financed.
 💡 Interested in how we can create an **#EnergyEfficiency** Aggregation platform for **#SustainableInvestments**?

🗣️ While we get our website ready, follow our hashtag **#energate_eu** and you will soon learn more about our advances!

Follow our partners and learn more about who we are Institute for **Institute for European Energy and Climate Policy Foundation (IEECP)** **DSS Lab**, **EPU-NTUA** **Engineering Ingegneria Informatica Spa** **REHVA Sustainable City** **Enerbrain Global** **Green Growth Institute** **EnerSave Capital Sarl** **GREENESCO SA** **LDK Consultants** **Commuty**

#energate_eu **#engineering** **#energy** **#projects** **#sustainable** **#sustainable** **#investments** **#finance** **#buildings** **#buildingservices**

Figure 15: Post about ENERGATE KoM on the ENERGATE's LinkedIn account

Campaigns, including hashtags and posts, will be regularly shared with partners via email to ensure consistency and track performance and mentions, so they can directly click and share. In such campaigns, target stakeholders such as relevant national and local organisation, policy makers, NGOs will always be tagged. In order to be able to track the project posts and mentions, every social media posts will have to include the project hashtag **#energate_eu**. Of course, the dissemination leader with support of project partners will look for the accounts of related LIFE projects and follow them, as well as use main hashtags to help LIFE accounts follow our activities - **#LIFEprogramme** and **#LIFEproject**, while tag on Twitter the **@LIFEprogramme** and for Clean Energy related projects **@cleanenergy_eu** and/or other relevant accounts. Several hashtags that will be used are: **#LIFEprogramme**, **#LIFEproject**, **#LIFEprojects**, **#LIFEis30**, **#ClimateNeutralEU**, **#EnergyTransition**, **#CleanEnergyEU**, **#EU2050**.

The number of posts, campaigns and content will be designed according to the different development of the project, focusing more on the share of the ongoing activities, events, public deliverables and shared results from the platform and the pilots. Each post will include the specific thematic hashtag and reference and tag to the key partners. The content will be produced in order for partners to post independently on their social media channel. To

guarantee the outreach to the main target audience, the partners will be invited to translate the content into their national language.

EPU NTUA's and other partners' existing accounts will be used to disseminate information on a regular basis and engage with target groups. Where possible, followers will be re-directed to the website to boost traffic. A shared Excel table of target accounts to follow or tag will be available in the Teams shared folder. All partners will be asked to fill it in with key actors at national and local levels.

Analytics will be used to understand if our strategy is working and redefine it if needed.

4.3. Newsletters

A series of e-newsletters will be released in electronic format through the [mailerlite](https://www.mailerlite.com/)³ platform, in order to promote the project and its events as well as to disseminate ENEREGATE outcomes. The e-Newsletter will be disseminated to relevant stakeholders at EU and MS level who will have already be subscriber and will have provided their consent to receive electronic communications regarding ENEREGATE progress, according to GDPR. Newsletters will be made available on the project website. A newsletter template which follows the project visual design has been created, while the first newsletter will disseminate the project general information and the kick-off meeting, the website and upcoming events. It will be released after M5 – May 2023, after the finalisation and publication of the website.

Figure 16: ENEREGATE Newsletter template

³ <https://www.mailerlite.com/>

E-Newsletters' content will be drafted by NTUA in collaboration with partners. It is envisaged that 1-2 newsletters per year will be distributed over the project lifetime.

To capitalise on the solid networks of the project partners, ENERGATE will have a project-branded newsletter that will take advantage of the network and contacts that NTUA has established but will also build on the partners' ones. To be updated with the project news, people will need to subscribe to ENERGATE Newsletter which is all GDPR-compliant. Of course, all the newsletters will be shared among partners networks, social media, newsletters, websites.

All partners (if applicable) will add content in their individual newsletters related to project activities, events, report, etc. So far ENERGATE has been mentioned [in the latest IEECP Newsletter](#), in an [article](#) published on the IEECP website.

Figure 17: IEECP article about ENERGATE project

5. ENERGATE Communication and Promotional Package

To kickstart the communication of ENERGATE, a promotional package has been developed and shared with all the consortium partners. This package includes a poster and a brochure that should support partners with pitching the project to relevant stakeholders.

Figure 18: ENERGATE brochure

Figure 19: ENER GATE poster

From the early stages of the project, the promotional package will be a living element. Therefore, more assets will be added later, such as a complementary slide deck with key project information, a one pager, fact sheets, and infographics that translate key project outcomes. Media pieces will also be developed on an opportunity basis and depending on the newsworthiness of project results.

The different formats of the assets in the promotional package should cover all the common situations where project information is needed; however, additional resources may be added if the consortium agrees on their relevance.

The promotional package will be available online to all partners for the whole duration of the project.

6. Scientific Publications

It is important that key results of ENERGATE are made available to the larger possible stakeholder group to ensure ownership and the scientific community is one of the project target groups. These activities include a number of scientific articles and concrete actions to facilitate the interaction/synergies with stakeholders from other related to ENERGATE projects and initiatives.

At least 2 papers are foreseen to be submitted to scientific journals or to a Special Issue, while at least 2 conference papers have been envisaged by the end of the project.

Up until now the following publications have been submitted and are accepted for publication:

- Charikleia Karakosta and Zoi Mylona (2022). A Methodological Framework Enhancing Energy Efficiency Investments in Buildings. 8th International Scientific-Business Conference titled: Leadership, Innovation, Management and Economics: Integrated Politics of Research – LIMEN 2022 (hybrid), 1 December 2022.
- Charikleia Karakosta, Zoi Mylona, Jason Papathanasiou, John Psarras (2023). Integrating Existing Knowledge to Accelerate Buildings Renovation Rates in Europe. In: Shaofeng Liu, Pascale Zaraté, Daouda Kamissoko, Isabelle Linden, Jason Papathanasiou (Eds.), Decision Support Systems XIII Decision Support Systems in An Uncertain World: The Contribution of Digital Twins (ICDSST 2023, LNBIP volume 474). Springer, In press.

7. Events

The event activities are linked to the dissemination of the project results through conferences and workshops organised externally or by the project consortium. The next paragraphs will dive deep into the different activities related to events.

7.1. Project-branded events

The ENERGATE partners will be encouraged to organize online and offline events whenever they have relevant messages and results to showcase. These events may be organized autonomously or under the umbrella of bigger events (such as the European Sustainable Energy Week).

At an early stage, at least two events are planned: one webinar to present the ENERGATE platform (when a demo version is ready for release); and one final event to present the results of the project. Additionally, four regional training workshops (in Latvia, Spain, Italy, and Greece) are being planned, although participation may be restricted if the local partner so decides.

7.2. External Events

External events can be categorized two-fold: events organized by other research projects; and events organized by European or national-level institutions.

7.2.1. Events organized by other projects

Being part of events organized by other projects allows ENERGATE to broaden its reach and increase visibility, as some relevant stakeholders might not have been reached yet by the project activities but follow other projects. Moreover, such events promote knowledge exchange and cooperation between consortia, bridging results and giving space to mutual inputs.

At such an early stage of the project, no external events organized by other projects are planned; however, opportunities may arise from the work being currently carried out to cluster ENERGATE with other EU-funded projects (see Section 7.1).

7.2.2. Events organized by other institutions

When ENERGATE takes part in external events that are organized outside the scope of EU-funded research projects, project reach also goes beyond the limits of the research world. In the particular case of this project, such visibility has a high impact, as the ENERGATE platform is being designed to serve users that are not researchers nor policymakers.

All partners of ENERGATE will be encouraged to participate in external events, so that the project is featured in such activities at least twice a year.

Considering the project's target stakeholders and objectives, a preliminary list of external events has been built as seen below. However, this list should be regarded as a reference and, simultaneously, as a living document: not only are these events not mandatory, but they are also not exclusive. The list should be completed throughout the project, following inputs and suggestions from all partners.

Table 3: ENERGate target events

<u>Event</u>	<u>Target audience</u>
<u>European Sustainable Energy Week</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers
<u>eceee summer study</u>	Industry, policy makers
<u>World Sustainable Energy Days</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers
<u>World Green Building Week</u>	Industry, policy makers
<u>European Energy Efficiency Day</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers
<u>EE Global Forum</u>	Industry, policy makers
<u>International PassivHouse Conference</u>	Industry, policy makers
<u>Enlit Europe</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers
<u>GreenBuild</u>	Industry, policy makers
<u>Building Greening</u>	Industry, policy makers
<u>International Energy Forum on Advanced Building Skins</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers
<u>Renovate Europe Days</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers
<u>Citizens Energy Forum</u>	Policy makers, researchers
<u>Mostra Convegno Expocomfort</u>	Industry, policy makers
<u>RECHARGE</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers
<u>Batibouw</u>	Industry
<u>Energy Efficiency Conference</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers
<u>Sustainable Places conference</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers
<u>SmartBuilt4EU, final meeting</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers
<u>MIPIM</u>	Industry
<u>ISEC Conference</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers
<u>Impact Days RENOWAVE.AT</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers
<u>Energy Evaluation Europe</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers
<u>Alliance to Save Energy</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers
<u>Energy Efficiency Finance Forum</u>	Industry, policy makers
<u>Berlin Green Investment Summit</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers

8. Synergies with other relevant EU initiatives

Science is, by nature, a compound work. Despite focusing on original initiatives, ENERGATE builds on knowledge produced by other projects – and it is also expected to inspire and support other research projects by providing inputs and information.

This exchange is only possible when synergies are in place: ENERGATE will communicate regularly with other projects and partner with them in joint activities, so to build a win-win scenario where all projects increase their reach, all receive valuable inputs, and all have the opportunity to frame their work within the work being carried out by others.

As a starting point, a preliminary list of relevant projects has already been laid out, as seen below. These projects were chosen because they either gather a community that includes ENERGATE target stakeholders, or they are carrying / have carried out research that can be of value to the ENERGATE work.

Synergies with other projects can result in a wide range of activities, including joint webinars and events; workshops; cross-dissemination; and guest-blogging.

Table 4: Synergies with other projects

Triple-A	Triple-A seeks to identify which investments can be considered as Triple-A investments, fostering sustainable growth while also having an extremely strong capacity to meet their commitments, already from the first stages of investments generation and preselection/ pre-evaluation.
AmBIENCE	AmBIENCE will provide new concepts and business models for performance guarantees of Active Buildings, combining savings from energy efficiency measures with additional savings and earnings resulting from the active control of assets leveraging for instance price based incentive contracts (Implicit Demand Response).
MATRYCS	MATRYCS aims to capitalise and combine existing modern technological breakthroughs in the areas of ML / DL and big data, in order to develop a new decision-making and data analytics solution for energy-efficient buildings.
COOLife	The CoolLIFE project aims to address the need for sustainable solutions to the EU's rising demand for space cooling in buildings. The project will develop open-source tools which encourage the consideration of green cooling solutions in public and private decision-making, planning, design, and implementation processes.
ENPOR	ENPOR aims to make energy vulnerability in the PRS visible and to test energy efficiency support schemes to address it.
FORTESIE	FORTESIE aims to design, demonstrate, validate and replicate innovative renovation packages in the building industry.
RENOVERTY	RENOVERTY will foster energy efficiency building upgrades in the energy poor households of Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) / South-eastern Europe (SEE) and Southern

	European countries (SE) by establishing the methodological and practical framework to build renovation roadmaps for vulnerable rural districts in a financially viable and socially just manner.
LEAF / LAUNCH / PROPEL	PROPEL aims to create an end-to-end service package to develop, sell, contract and finance energy efficiency initiatives at scale. This includes the LAUNCH standardised materials and those developed under PROPEL - the loan application and KYC guidelines, ESG module for loan applications and standardised contact signature authentication.
TRUSTEE	TRUSTEE will provide the first quantification of the many-to-many relationship between ecosystem services and economic development taking into account rural diversity and different spatial scales.
SEIFA	The SEIFA project is an initiative co-funded by the European Commission with the aim to increase sustainable energy investments in the CEE region-based industrial companies.
InEExS	The core concept of the LIFE project InEExS is the deployment of integrated energy services across sectors and carriers, and the tokenization of energy saving data in a public blockchain to facilitate cooperation among market segments and actors.
SENSEI	SENSEI has been investigating the use of Pay-for-Performance (P4P) schemes to aggregate retrofit projects, improve the effectiveness of subsidy programmes, and reward energy efficiency as an energy resource and a grid service. P4P schemes have been applied in the U.S. for many years and based on the lessons learned, SENSEI has been developing knowledge and insights into how P4P can benefit market players such as ESCO's, building owners and energy providers and not least, how improving energy efficiency rates can help us all reach the climate goals and mitigate the energy crisis.
AUDIT2MEASURE	<p>AUDIT-TO-MEASURE (Leading business towards climate neutrality by speeding up the uptake of energy efficiency measures from the energy audits) will help companies to uptake measures necessary to reduce their energy consumption, thus supporting their energy transition.</p> <p>AUDIT-TO-MEASURE will develop and implement a new engagement strategy (called "Audit2Action") to put into action the opportunities emerging from energy audits.</p>
JUSTEM	Following a double-sided approach, the project will help regional authorities to develop and implement plans that are sensitive to local impacts, while engaging citizens in capacity building activities tailored to increase acceptance and build confidence in a coal-free economy.

REGIO1ST	<p>Regio1st raises awareness about the Energy Efficiency First principle (EE1st) among regional governments and their agencies and supports them to make related decisions in their planning. It does so through the provision of appropriate guidance to regional authorities to embed the EE1st principle in their decisions and in the implementation of their energy plans departing from six participant regions and expanding to over 100 regions in the EU. It establishes a community of practice for EE1st in cooperation with the Covenant of Mayors to ensure political commitment of regional authorities and strengthens the enforcement of the Multilevel Climate and Energy Dialogue provision, with particular focus on ownership and acceptance of the principle from stakeholders at all levels.</p>
EN-Track	<p>The goal of EN-TRACK is to create a one-stop shop platform with standardized data related to the energy efficiency performance of the public and private building stock. Enabling interoperability with most currently active databases and tools, this will lead to an unambiguous data exchange based services ecosystem with low transactional costs.</p>
BD4ENERGY	<p>BD4NRG envisions to confront big data management challenges for the energy sector, giving a competitive edge to the European stakeholders to improve decision making and at the same time to open new market opportunities.</p>
EEFIG 3	<p>An open-source initiative to up-scale energy efficiency investments in Europe through the improved sharing and transparent analysis of existing projects in Buildings and Industry</p>
MBENEFITS	<p>The goal of the M-BENEFITS project is to train and build the capacity of energy-efficiency experts to evaluate all benefits (i.e. not only the energy-savings benefits) of industrial and building/tertiary sector focused energy-efficiency projects (i.e., industrial production sites, administrative and commercial buildings).</p>
EENVEST	<p>The aim of EEnvest is the creation of a tool (a web-based search and match platform) which investors can use to evaluate the risk of investment in energy efficiency for buildings. The web-based search platform will match the demand and offer of buildings to be retrofitted with funding available from external financiers.</p>
QUEST	<p>QUEST defines, measures and supports quality in science communication. The project will develop tools and guidelines for improving effectiveness in dialogue between science and wider publics.</p>
RENONBILL	<p>RenOnBill aims to scale up investments towards deep energy renovations of residential buildings by promoting the development and implementation of on-bill schemes, based</p>

	on the cooperation between energy utilities and financial institutions.
U-CERT	The project will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduce a next generation of user-centred Energy Performance Assessment and Certification Scheme - Facilitate convergence of quality and reliability - Encourage the development and application of holistic user-centred innovative solutions - Encourage and support end-users in decision making
BIGG	The BIGG project aims at demonstrating the application of big data technologies and data analytic techniques for the complete buildings life-cycle of more than 4000 buildings in 6 large-scale pilot test-beds.
BUILTHUB	The project seeks to develop a roadmap to continuously enhance the data needed to decide on building-related policy and business for involved stakeholders through a community and its data hub. It seeks to positively disrupt policy and market decision-making through a continuously community-enhanced evidence base.
BEYOND	BEYOND project's objective is to implement the necessary hardware and software to demonstrate peer-to-peer electricity trading platforms and perform flexible mechanisms (demand response or battery scheduling) to maximize the deployment of renewables. Austria, Norway and Ireland are the countries holding these pilots.

At the time of this report, ENERGATE has joined a cluster with InEExS, REGIO1ST, AUDIT2MEASURE, JUSTEM, BUS-REGRoUP, and REGIO1ST to discuss opportunities for cross-dissemination and joint events.

The project has also been featured in the final newsletter of SENSEI, so to engage target stakeholders that belong to the audience of that project.

All activities resulting from inter-project synergies are monitored in a single file that is shared with all consortium partners.

9. Communication and Dissemination activities: reporting methodology (KPIs and monitoring)

A Communication & Dissemination monitoring tool have been created at project's start. All partners will be responsible to report their activities during the overall duration of ENERGATE.

Table 5: ENERGATE communication tools and planning

Communication Tool	Time / Frequency	Monitoring Measure
Project Identity	M2	NA
ENERGATE Website	M5 / At least 5,000 unique visitors per year of & 15% return visitors	Website statistics (Google Analytics)
Dedicated project page on the beneficiaries' website	M5	NA
Social Media	During the project implementation / At least 30 announcements, reports' posts, etc. in partners' and relevant sites and platforms	All social networks have their own monitoring tools
Newsletters	1-2/year sent to people registered on the ENERGATE website	Newsletter's tool report, including openings, clicks & list of recipients
Brochure	M5 / 200 downloads per year, printed version distributed in 1,000 copies	Number of downloads on the website, number of copies distributed & were tracked
One pager	Events distribution and online presentation	List of events where exposed, photos & list of participants, number of downloads on the website
Infographics and factsheet	WP2 reports, financing typologies, platform, presenting the pilots from WP4, etc.	Number of downloads on the website, number of copies distributed & were tracked

Scientific Papers	All along project duration / At least 2 papers submitted to scientific journals or to a Special Issue, at least 2 conference papers	Number of papers submitted
Media pieces	During the project implementation / 3 articles or press releases per partner, readership expected: 1000 people / At least 10 references, articles and mentions in relevant communications and media	Media monitoring performed regularly. Copies will be shared on our website.
Clustering activities	Clustering via website, social media and joint development of activities	Monitoring of publications (analytics) and meetings (lists)
Events	Webinars, 4 Regional Training Workshops, EU final event in Brussels	Agenda, Participants' lists

10. Planned activities

In this section we provide an overview of the planned communication & dissemination activities for the upcoming year of the project as well as the communication activities already conducted until M3. Partners have identified relevant events, workshops and other communication activities relevant for the project. In the next update of this deliverable, we will provide an overview of all communication and dissemination activities that will have been done until the end of the project implementation.

Table 6 ENERGate list of planned activities M1-M12

Time Period	Partner	Activity Title	Target Group (s)	Related task
M1 – M3	NTUA	Project social media account creation (Twitter, LinkedIn)	All	T7.3 Communication package of Tools and material
M1 – ongoing	NTUA	ENERGATE website creation	All	T7.3 Communication package of Tools and material
M1-M3	REHVA	ENERGATE visual identity package	All	T7.3 Communication package of Tools and material
M1-ongoing	IEECP	ENERGATE promotional package	All	T7.3 Communication package of Tools and material
M1-M3	All	Dedicated ENERGate page on partners' website	All	T.7.2 Digital outreach
M1-M6	All	Pilots presentation and promotion on website and Social Media	All	T.7.2 Digital outreach
M1-M6	All	Listing ENERGate on relevant platforms (SmartBuilt4EU, ECTP (European Construction Technology Platform), ...)	All	T.7.2 Digital outreach

M2	IEECP	Overview article on IEECP website with key info about the project	All	T.7.2 Digital outreach
M3	IEECP	Feature project content on IEECP newsletter	All	T.7.2 Digital outreach
M6-M12	NTUA	1 st Newsletter issue	All	T.7.2 Digital outreach
M6-M12	NTUA	ENERGATE promotional (animation) video	All	T.7.2 Digital outreach
M6-M12	All	Participation to at least 1 institutional event (European Sustainable Energy Week, World Sustainable Energy Days)	All	T.7.4 Communication, dissemination, and networking boosters
M6-M12	REHVA - NTUA	REHVA Journal overview article of ENEREGATE objectives	All	T.7.2 Digital outreach
M12	All	Organisation of a BuildUp webinar introducing ENEREGATE to wide audience (potentially together with sister project)	All	T.7.4 Communication, dissemination, and networking boosters

11. ANNEX I- Logo selection process

Before the kick-off meeting NTUA and REHVA worked on eight different logo propositions to be presented during the kick-off to all partners. Partners have then been asked to select their favourite option via a google form (<https://forms.gle/sEgKaVnWnkdmLYj6>).

ENERGATE LOGO
Which logo better represents ENERGATE?

rehvahvac@gmail.com (not shared) [Switch account](#)

Option 1

ENERGATE ENERGATE
Energy Efficiency Marketplace

Option 1

Option 2

ENERGATE ENERGATE

Option 2

Option 5

Option 5

Option 6

Option 6

Option 3

ENERGATE
ENERGY EFFICIENCY MARKETPLACE

Option 3

Option 7

Option 7

Option 4

ENERGATE ENERGY EFFICIENCY MARKETPLACE
ENERGATE ENERGY EFFICIENCY MARKETPLACE

Option 4

Option 8

ENERGATE
ENERGY EFFICIENCY MARKETPLACE

Option 8

12. ANNEX II- ENERGATE Brand Manual

The ENERGATE brand manual is available in the project repository and below.

OUR TEAM

See you online!

energate-project.eu

[ENERGATE Project](#)

[#energate_eu](#)

BRAND BOOK **GUIDELINES**

Identity Manual

An **Overview**

This document communicates the brand identity of ENERGATE.
Clearly articulating the Mission, Values and person for the design
of all subsequent brand artifacts.

Table Of **Contents**

. Verbal Identity	01 - 04
. Logo Guidelines	05 - 08
. Typography	09 - 10
. Colors	11 - 15

Verbal Identity

About

ENERGATE aims to facilitate the creation of an effective, ICT-enabled, energy efficiency marketplace bringing together energy services and sustainable finance to accelerate the renovation rate of buildings by increasing the chances for projects to be financed.

ENERGATE envisions to transform the complex set of decision-making actions for targeted groups, even to non-experts, into a user-friendly and single-entry service.

Words

Energy
Efficiency

Finance

Building
Data

Building

Sustainable

User
Friendly

Characteristics

Logo Guidelines

ENERGATE Logo

The Official full fledged logo of ENERGATE that should be used in all instance related to this brand.

Logo Construction

Exclusion Zone & Variations

1x amount of space should the exclusion zone.
It is Prohibited to use any sort of artworks,
typography or any other graphical artifacts
between this 1x exclusion zone.

Exclusion Zone & Variations

1x amount of space should the exclusion zone.
It is Prohibited to use any sort of artworks,
typography or any other graphical artifacts
between this 1x exclusion zone.

Reversed & Single Color

Don't

Don't distort the logo in any way

Don't change the colors to outline

Don't add drop shadow

Don't rotate the logo

Typography Guidelines

Logo
Fonts

Logo

Logo Name

BEBAS KAI

ENERGATE

Slogan Font

BEBAS KAI

ENERGY EFFICIENCY MARKETPLACE

Brand Fonts

Avenir

Avenir Light

Avenir Book

Avenir Italic

Avenir Medium

Avenir Medium Italic

Avenir Black

Avenir Black Italic

Avenir Heavy

Avenir Heavy Italic

What is a paragraph?

Paragraphs are the building blocks of papers. Many students define paragraphs in terms of length: a paragraph is a group of at least five sentences, a paragraph is half a page long, etc. In reality, though, the unity and coherence of ideas among sentences is what constitutes a paragraph.

Brand Colors

Logo Colors

Hex: #1683C8
R: 22
G: 131
B: 200

Hex: #305C83
R: 48
G: 92
B: 131

Hex: #000000
R: 00
G: 00
B: 00

A network diagram with nodes and connections in shades of blue and grey. The nodes are represented by circles of varying sizes, and the connections are thin lines. The overall structure is a complex, interconnected web. The text "Thank you" is centered in the middle of the image.

Thank you